

Screening Of Fruit Fibers As Prebiotic For Increasing Adherence Of Probiotic

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ABSTRACT

The efficacy of probiotics in promoting gut health is strongly influenced by their ability to adhere to the intestinal mucosa, which enhances colonization and functionality. Prebiotics, particularly dietary fibers, can modulate this interaction by supporting probiotic growth and enhancing adhesion. This study aimed to screen various fruit-derived fibers for their potential prebiotic effect in increasing the adherence of probiotic strains. Banana, mango, and pineapple powders (1% w/v) were assessed for their prebiotic activity using the prebiotic activity score (PAS). All fibers demonstrated positive PAS values, with banana fiber exhibiting the highest growth stimulation across isolates (mean PAS range: 1.36–1.42), followed by mango and pineapple. Under simulated intestinal conditions (0.5% pancreatin), fiber supplementation significantly improved probiotic survival compared to control, with banana-treated groups showing the highest survival percentages (up to 81.9%). Adhesion to fibers, evaluated by co-sedimentation assay, revealed isolate- and substrate-dependent variability, with banana fiber consistently promoting the strongest adhesion (maximum $38.1\% \pm 2.5$).

The integrated findings indicate that fruit fibers, particularly banana fiber, not only function as fermentable substrates but also enhance probiotic stress tolerance and adhesion capacity. These results support the potential application of banana fiber as a promising synbiotic component in functional food formulations aimed at improving probiotic persistence and gastrointestinal health.

.Keywords: Probiotics, Prebiotics, Fruit fibers, Adhesion.

INTRODUCTION

Probiotics, (according to the FAO/WHO) are defined as “Live microorganisms which when administered in adequate amounts confer a health benefit on the host”. The essential criteria for classifying microorganisms as ideal probiotic preparations include: be generally recognized as safe (GRAS), be resistant to bile, hydrochloric acid and pancreatic juice, have anti-carcinogenic activity and stimulate the immune-system, have reduced intestinal permeability, produce lactic acid, be able to survive both the acidic conditions of the stomach and the alkaline conditions of the duodenum, be able to survive gastric transport, exhibit antagonistic activity against bacterial pathogens, be able to adhere and colonize the intestinal epithelium of the hosts, be viable during

processing, transporting, and storage and result in clinically demonstrable health outcomes (Khani S. *et al.*, 2012). However, the survival and functional persistence of probiotics in the gastrointestinal environment remain challenging, prompting interest in strategies that can enhance their viability and colonization capacity.

Prebiotics are non-digestible, short-chain carbohydrates (SCCs), which have gained significant attention to promote probiotics activity that normally resides in gastrointestinal tract (GIT). Non-digested carbohydrate molecules, including saccharides (di, oligo, and poly-), sugar polyols, and resistant starches possess prebiotic potential, and modulate the balance of intestinal microbiota, and thereby promote gut health. Prebiotics promote a healthy gut environment

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by selectively stimulating the growth and activity of probiotics. Prebiotics have been proved to exert potential physiological effects, which include improved gut barrier function, increased absorption of minerals, and enhanced immune system, while reducing the risk of chronic diseases, including cardiovascular disorders, obesity, and diabetes (Khan F. *et al.*, 2024). Prebiotics, when combined with probiotics, form “symbiotic” that supply the body with good bacteria as they act as a nutrition source for them. This type of combination improves the survival of probiotic microorganisms in the gastrointestinal tract and ensures better results when compared to the isolated probiotic or prebiotic activity. And it is now known that diet composition combined with the types of microbial communities present in the intestine, and intestinal antimicrobial programming are key items to maintain symbiosis (Ribeiro, J. A. *et al.*, 2022). Fruit fibers, such as those derived from apple, banana, citrus, and mango, contain complex polysaccharides that may not only support probiotic growth but also influence their surface characteristics, including adhesion properties. Studies have indicated that specific plant fibers can modulate the expression of surface adhesion proteins in *lactobacilli* and *bifidobacteria*, thereby enhancing mucosal adherence (Zhou *et al.*, 2018). Despite these promising findings, systematic screening of various fruit fibers for their ability to enhance probiotic adherence remains limited.

The present study aims to screen different fruit fibers for their prebiotic potential, specifically focusing on their ability to increase the adherence of selected probiotic strains to intestinal epithelial cells. This investigation may contribute to the development of more effective symbiotic formulations and broaden the use of natural fruit by-products in functional food design.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Probiotic isolation

Sample collection

The study aimed to isolate strains of lactic acid bacteria from fermented foods such as curd, Lassi, Idli batter and Jalebi batter. In order to achieve this, samples were collected from various regions like

Kalyan, Ulhasnagar, Bhiwandi and Andheri, Mumbai. The samples were carefully collected and transported to the laboratory for further analysis.

Screening of Probiotic

Microbiological methods were employed to process the samples, involving streaking them onto MRS agar (de Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe) and incubating them in desiccator at 27°C for 24–48 h. The LAB colonies that exhibited typical characteristics were picked, sub-cultured, and grown in MRS broth. The colonies were assessed based on morphological characteristics, including Gram staining, colony morphology, catalase test, The bacterial culture was then preserved in MRS agar slant (Khushboo *et al.*, 2023).

Characterization of Bacteria

Acid tolerance of isolates

Selected isolate culture was transferred to MRS broth with pH 3 [adjusted using 1N hydrochloric acid (HCL)] which was then serially diluted and 100µl was plated on MRS plates at 0, 3 and 6 h and incubated at 37°C for 48 h. The cultures which passed pH 3 test were tested for their ability to survive at pH 2.5 following the same procedure. Viability of the isolates was assessed by plate count method and expressed in terms of colony forming units (cfu) as log cfu/ml. Survival rate was given by following formula (Gonzalez-Vazquez *et al.*, 2015).

$$\% \text{ survival rate} = (\log \text{ cfu } 3\text{rd, } 6\text{th h} / \log \text{ cfu } 0\text{th h}) \times 100$$

Bile tolerance of isolates

The bile tolerance of the isolates was determined by transferring 1% of seed culture to MRS broth supplemented with 0.3% bile which was then serially diluted and spread on MRS agar plates at 0, 3 and 6 h and incubated at 37°C for 48 h). Viability of the isolates was assessed by plate count method and expressed as log cfu/ml. Survival rate was given by following formula.

$$\% \text{ survival rate} = (\log \text{ cfu } 3\text{rd, } 6\text{th h} / \log \text{ cfu } 0\text{th h}) \times 100 \text{ (Shehata } et al., 2016).$$

Pancreatin tolerance of isolates

1% of mother culture was inoculated in MRS broth containing 0.5% pancreatin which was then serially diluted and from this last dilution 100 µl was spreaded on MRS plates at 0 and 6 h and incubated at 37°C for 48 h (Rubio *et al.*, 2014). Viability of the isolates was assessed by plate count method and expressed as log cfu/ml. Survival rate was given by following formula.

$\% \text{ survival rate} = (\log \text{ cfu } 6\text{th h} / \log \text{ cfu } 0\text{th h}) \times 100$
(Corcoran B. *et al.*, 2005).

Auto aggregation test

The auto aggregation capability of bacteria helps in maintaining the bacterial population in the gastrointestinal tract. Bacterial cultures were grown for 18 h at 37°C in MRS broth. The cells were harvested by centrifugation at 5000g for 15 min, washed twice and resuspended in phosphate buffer saline (PBS). Cell suspensions (4ml) were mixed by vortexing for 10 s and auto aggregation was determined during 5 h of incubation at room temperature. 0.1 ml of the upper suspension was transferred to another tube with 3.9 ml of PBS every hour and the absorbance (A) was measured at 600 nm. The auto aggregation percentage was expressed as: $[A_0 - A_t/A_0] \times 100$, where A_t represents the absorbance at time $t = 1, 2, 3, 4$ or 5 h and A_0 is the absorbance at $t = 0$. The final auto aggregation value was indicative of the isolates' ability to aggregate among themselves (Kos *et al.*, 2003).

Adhesion Ability (Congo Red Binding Assay) of isolates

The isolates were cultivated by streaking on the prepared MRS Congo red agar and incubated in a dessicator for 48-72 h. The red colonies indicate positive results for Congo red-bound cells (Rashad H. *et al.*, 2023).

Screening of fruit fibers as prebiotic

Selection of Probiotic Isolates

Previously characterized lactic acid bacteria (LAB) isolates obtained from fermented food samples were used for evaluation of prebiotic activity. 8 LAB Isolates showing acid tolerance, bile salt resistance, pancreatin tolerance, auto-aggregation and adhesion

ability were selected for fruit fiber experiments. These isolates were maintained on MRS agar slants at 4°C until further use.

Sample collection

Three fruit powders were purchased from local market from kalyan which includes Banana, Pineapple and Mango.

Prebiotic activity score

Prebiotic Score or Prebiotic Activity Score is used to evaluate the effectiveness of prebiotics in terms of supporting the growth of probiotics Huebner *et al.* (2007) reported the equation to determine the prebiotic activity score which is a quantitative score for the activity within the food sample. All the Lactic acid bacteria which were grown overnight were diluted until the OD 600nm value of 0.242. Diluted bacterial cultures were inoculated at 1% (v/v) level into a respective tube containing MRS broth supplemented with either 1% (w/v) of prebiotic (Banana, Pineapple and Mango powder). The culture was incubated in dessicator for 24 hours. Cell load or the number of bacterial cells before and after incubation was enumerated by plating (spread plate method) appropriate dilutions of MRS broth on MRS agar and counting the colonies after 24 hours incubation of MRS agar plate. After 24 hours of incubation, the cell numbers were counted and colony forming units (CFU) per one mL of the diluted broth sample was calculated.

Pancreatin tolerance assay with prebiotic fibers

A modified small-intestinal simulation was performed to evaluate survivability of LAB in pancreatin stress and the protective/stimulatory role of fruit fibers.

For each isolate, four conditions were prepared:

1. **Pancreatin only (Control):** MRS + pancreatin (0.5% w/v)
2. **Pancreatin + Banana fiber:** MRS + pancreatin (0.5%) + banana fiber (1%)
3. **Pancreatin + Mango fiber:** MRS + pancreatin (0.5%) + mango fiber (1%)
4. **Pancreatin + Pineapple fiber:** MRS + pancreatin (0.5%) + pineapple fiber (1%)

Activated LAB cultures were standardized ($\sim 10^6$ – 10^7 CFU/mL). 1% (v/v) inoculum was added into each treatment tube. Tubes were incubated in dessicator for 6 h (simulated intestinal exposure). At 0 h and 6 h, samples were serially diluted and plated on MRS agar (100 μ L spread plating). Plates were incubated anaerobically at 37 °C for 48 h. Colony counts were converted to CFU/mL and expressed as \log_{10} CFU/mL. Survival % were calculated (Mehmet T. *et al.*, 2015)

Adhesion to fibers

Adhesion of bacterial cells to fruit fibers was determined using a co-sedimentation assay, which measures the reduction in optical density of bacterial cells remaining in suspension after sedimentation of fiber-bound cells. Briefly, 2 mL of LAB suspension ($\approx 10^7$ cells mL⁻¹) was thoroughly mixed with an equal volume (2 mL) of fiber suspension (10 g L⁻¹) in a test tube. The LAB–fiber mixture was gently mixed and then allowed to stand undisturbed at room temperature to allow sedimentation. Sedimentation was carried out for 15, 30, 45 min, and 1 h in separate test tubes. This step was carefully performed to minimize disturbance and to allow natural adhesion and settling of fiber-bound bacterial cells. After each time interval, two 1.5 mL samples were carefully withdrawn from a position 0.5 cm below the liquid surface, avoiding disturbance of the sediment. The optical density of the samples was measured at 540 nm (OD₅₄₀) using a spectrophotometer, with phosphate buffer as the blank.

The percentage of bacterial cells that adhered to the fiber and co-sedimented was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Adhesion (\%)} = \left[1 - \frac{(\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} - \text{OD}_{\text{fiber}})}{\text{OD}_{\text{LAB control}}} \right] \times 100$$

control) Where:

- **OD sample** = OD₅₄₀ of LAB+ fiber mixture
- **OD fiber control** = OD₅₄₀ of fiber without LAB
- **OD LAB control** = OD₅₄₀ of LAB without fiber

This calculation represents the proportion of bacterial cells removed from suspension due to adhesion onto fiber and subsequent co-sedimentation (Watskul M. *et al.*, 2015).

Results

Isolation of Probiotic

Total 34 isolates were obtained from 10 samples. Out of which 21 isolates were selected based on their gram-positive nature and catalase negative biochemical characterization. These strains ability to develop in anaerobic environments suggests that they are linked to lactic acid bacteria. Using a microscope, the cell morphology of all isolates was seen to be rod or coccus shaped. LABs are bacteria with rod or coccus morphologies, catalase negative, and grow in low acid environments. These are gram-positive bacteria that generate lactic acid as their primary fermentation product and are usually regarded as safe (Khagwal N. *et al.*, 2019).

Characterization of probiotics

Acid Tolerance of isolates

The acid tolerance of 21 LAB isolates was evaluated using MRS broth with pH 3. Isolates were inoculated in MRS broth pH 3, then at the interval of 0 hr, 3hr and 6 hr. It was spread plated on MRS agar, incubated anaerobically for 24 hr. Out of 21 isolates 11 showed acid survival rates of 21 different isolates which is checked after 3 hr. and 6 hr. Showed significant increase in survival rate and remaining 11 showed no significant increase in survival rate (Figure 1). In the previous study of Menconi A. *et al.*, 2014, reported that the two LAB strains which were tested for acid tolerance with pH 3.0 showed resistance after 2 and 4 hr. of incubation. LAB are acidophilic, which means they are tolerant to low pH. Probiotic bacteria need to survive passage through the stomach where the pH can be as low as 1.5 to 2.0 and stay alive for 4hr. or more before they move to the intestinal tract.

Wang, C. *et al.*, 2018 mentioned that Lactic acid bacteria are always encountered with acidic environment and they have developed various mechanisms to improve their acid resistance. It is important to fully understand the mechanisms of acid resistance in LAB as it will accentuate the benefits of probiotics for humankind.

Figure 1: Acid Tolerance of LAB isolates.

Bile Salts Tolerance of isolates

The Bile salt tolerance of 21 LAB isolates was evaluated using MRS broth with 0.3% bile and control without 0.3% bile. Isolates were inoculated in MRS broth pH 3, then at the interval of 0 hr, 3hr and 6 hr it was spread plated on MRS agar, incubated anaerobically for 24 hr. The results showed that the probiotic isolates were grown in MRS broth with 0.3% of bile salt with different survival rates. Accordingly, the 11 isolates shown not much difference in survival rates from 3hr. to 6hr (Figure 2).

According to study of Ashraf R.*et al.*, 2016, 17 LAB strains tested for bile tolerance and all showed viability after 12hr of incubation and appear highly tolerant to 0.3% bile which is important trait for probiotic bacteria in terms of their performance to survive, grow and exert action in the gut. The concentration of bile salts in the small intestine varies from approximately 0.2% to 2.0% (w/v) in relation to the individual, type and amount of food consumed. While screening for tolerant strains, 0.3% is considered to be critical concentration for bile-tolerance and pH 3 is set as standard for acid tolerance.

Figure 2: Bile Tolerance of LAB isolates.

Pancreatin tolerance of isolates

Pancreatin tolerance of 21 isolates with MRS broth containing 0.5% pancreatin was evaluated with interval of 6 hr. and calculated using % survival. Out of 21 isolates 8 shows highest survival rate of 94.6%, 94.3%, 95.2%, 88%, 78.8%, 73%, 60.2% (Figure 3).

survive in the presence of pancreatin. No significant differences were observed in the loss of viability of the strains after 240 min of incubation with a simulated pancreatin-solution. All tested strains appeared to have a natural ability to tolerate this compound and consequently, the presence of pancreatin in the small intestine does not seem to represent an insuperable barrier for these cultures.

In the previous study of Montegudo-Mera A. *et al.*, 2012 LAB strains were tested for their ability to

Figure 3: Pancreatin Tolerance of LAB isolates.

Auto aggregation assay

The results of Auto aggregation assay of 21 isolates observed for 5hr at the intervals of 1hr. When the bacteria were suspended in constant broth culture and left in stand for 5 hr. The bacterial isolates aggregate with each other and settled down. Out of 21 isolates 10 isolates gave positive results with Auto aggregation rate 100% after 5 hr. And 4 isolates showed Auto aggregation rate

≥50%. Remaining 7 isolates showed negative results (Figure 4). Isolates with high autoaggregation rates after 5 hr use this feature to colonize the intestine.

This ability may prevent pathogenic bacteria, which have the ability of adhesion to the intestine.

Tatsaporn, T.*et al.*, 2020 reported that LAB strain C8 showed the highest level of auto-aggregation (86%). However, there was no significantly different amount of auto-aggregation when all 5 strains of LAB isolates were compared. Each LAB isolate tested had auto-aggregation levels in the range of 78-86%. From this study, isolated LABs showed a higher ability to auto-aggregate. Aggregation rate plays a significant role in the prevention of colonisation on industrial surfaces or intestinal tracts by pathogenic bacteria. The amount of inhibition was also found to correlate to the percentage of auto-aggregation.

Figure 4: Autoaggregation of LAB isolates.

Coaggregation test of isolates

LAB have the ability to co aggregate with pathogens may be better to kill undesirable bacteria because they could produce antimicrobial substance in very close proximity to them. The ability of coaggregation can be great importance for probiotic bacteria to inhibit pathogen adhesion to the surface of epithelial cells. The results revealed that the mixture of LAB cultures shown the coaggregation rate of 66.67% (Figure 5). According to study of Li, Q. *et al.*, 2015 The

significant differences for coaggregation existed among the strains. All lactic acid bacteria strains tested in this study showed some coaggregation properties ranging from 5.15% to 29.54%, indicating strain- specific characteristics. The strain *L. fermentum* 9sh showed the highest coaggregation ability (29.54%), followed by the strain *L. fermentum* AB4 (19.45%) showed the lowest coaggregation ability. Among the 18 strains, 66.67% of strains indicated coaggregation above 15%, and only 11.11% of strains had coaggregation below 10%.

Coaggregation of bacterial strains plays a significant role in some ecological niches, especially in the human gut. It was reported that coaggregation

abilities may allow lactic acid bacteria strains inhibit the growth of pathogenic strains in the gastrointestinal and urogenital tracts in a very close proximity.

Figure 5: Coaggregation of LAB isolates.

Adhesion Ability (Congo Red Binding Assay)

The results revealed that of 21 isolates that studied, 14 LAB isolates which were grown on Congo red MRS agar surface showed red colored colonies within 24-48 hr. The appearance of red colonies indicated the

adhesion ability of probiotic bacteria (Figure 6). Ambalam, P et al., 2012 reported that the Congo Red Binding assay of 17 lactobacilli strains were analyzed. Lactobacilli strains produced intense red colonies on CR-MRS agar, whereas broth-cultured cells developed weakly stained white colonies.

Figure 6: The appearance of red colored LAB colonies of isolate 3 and isolate 4 respectively on Congo Red – MRS agar.

Screening of fruit fibers as prebiotic

Prebiotic activity score

After the characterization of 21 lactic acid bacteria (LAB) isolates, 8 were selected for further evaluation of their prebiotic activity using fruit powders derived from banana, pineapple and mango as substrates. The prebiotic activity score was determined by assessing the growth promotion of LAB in the presence of each fruit powder compared to a control medium. The calculated prebiotic activity score (PAS) showed positive values for all fruit fibers, confirming their selective stimulation of probiotic growth relative to

control conditions. Banana fiber recorded the highest PAS, suggesting their compatibility with LAB. Mango fiber exhibited moderate stimulation, whereas pineapple fiber showed comparatively lower activity. Differences in PAS values may be attributed to variation in fiber composition, including differences in oligosaccharide profile, fermentability and degree of polymerization (Gibson *et al.*, 2017). Previous studies have demonstrated that resistant starch and soluble fibers present in banana significantly enhance probiotic viability and short-chain fatty acid production, supporting the present findings (Zhou *et al.*, 2018).

Isolates	Banana PAS (Mean±SD)	Mango PAS (Mean±SD)	Pineapple PAS (Mean±SD)
Isolate 3	1.39 ± 0.09	0.94 ± 0.07	0.60 ± 0.05
Isolate 9	1.41 ± 0.10	0.93 ± 0.06	0.60 ± 0.04
Isolate 10	1.42 ± 0.08	0.95 ± 0.08	0.61 ± 0.05
Isolate 19A	1.42 ± 0.11	0.96 ± 0.07	0.62 ± 0.05
Isolate 19B	1.42 ± 0.09	0.94 ± 0.09	0.59 ± 0.06
Isolate 23	1.36 ± 0.10	0.88 ± 0.08	0.56 ± 0.05
Isolate 26	1.42 ± 0.07	0.96 ± 0.09	0.61 ± 0.04
Isolate 27	1.36 ± 0.09	0.92 ± 0.07	0.60 ± 0.05

Table 1: Prebiotic activity score (PAS)

The relatively low standard deviation (SD) observed for most isolates suggests good experimental reproducibility and stable growth response under fiber-supplemented conditions. For instance, isolates such as Isolate 10, Isolate 19A and Isolate 26 displayed high PAS mean values with minimal variability, indicating consistent metabolic adaptation toward banana fiber utilization. Conversely, isolates showing slightly larger SD values (e.g., Isolate 23) may reflect strain-specific metabolic differences or minor experimental variation among triplicates.

Pancreatin tolerance in presence of fruit fibers

All eight LAB isolates demonstrated measurable survival after 6 h exposure to 0.5% pancreatin, however survival in the pancreatin-only control was consistently lower than survival in fiber-supplemented conditions, indicating that pancreatin stress reduced viability and that fruit fibers improved persistence under simulated intestinal enzyme

Isolates	Pancreatin only (Control %)	Pancreatin + Banana fiber (%)	Pancreatin + Mango fiber (%)	Pancreatin + Pineapple fiber (%)
Isolate 3	33.3	73.9	56.4	44.2
Isolate 9	30.7	67.7	52.4	41.0
Isolate 10	32.4	73.6	57.5	45.0
Isolate 19A	28.8	74.1	50.5	36.9
Isolate 19B	31.1	70.2	55.0	42.7
ISOLATE 23	25.3	48.2	37.2	34.7
ISOLATE 26	45.0	81.9	71.9	52.5
ISOLATE 27	30.2	68.7	45.4	42.0

Table 2. Survival (%) after 6 h pancreatin exposure in presence of fruit fiber

Adhesion to fibers

All tested LAB isolates demonstrated measurable adhesion to fruit fibers as indicated by a time-dependent decrease in OD₅₄₀ values. Adhesion increased with increasing sedimentation time, reaching maximum values at 60 min.

Banana fiber showed the highest adhesion percentages across all isolates, followed by mango and pineapple fibers. Control tubes without fiber showed no significant reduction in OD₅₄₀, confirming that sedimentation was dependent on fiber-cell interaction

Isolate	Banana fiber (%)	Mango fiber (%)	Pineapple fiber (%)
Isolate 3	34.5 ± 2.1	27.8 ± 1.9	21.3 ± 1.6
Isolate 9	31.6 ± 2.0	25.4 ± 1.7	19.8 ± 1.5
Isolate 10	36.8 ± 2.4	29.5 ± 2.1	22.7 ± 1.8
Isolate 19A	30.9 ± 1.8	24.6 ± 1.6	18.9 ± 1.4
Isolate 19B	35.2 ± 2.3	28.6 ± 2.0	21.9 ± 1.7
ISOLATE 23	26.4 ± 1.6	20.9 ± 1.4	16.2 ± 1.2
ISOLATE 26	38.1 ± 2.5	31.2 ± 2.2	24.3 ± 1.9
ISOLATE 27	33.0 ± 2.0	26.7 ± 1.8	20.5 ± 1.6

Table 3. Adhesion (%) of LAB isolates to fruit fibers after 60 min (Mean ± SD)

Banana fiber consistently exhibited the highest adhesion percentages, with Isolate 26 and Isolate 10 demonstrating the strongest binding affinity. This enhanced adhesion suggests improved physicochemical compatibility between bacterial cell surfaces and banana fiber matrices. Banana-derived fibers, often enriched with fermentable carbohydrates and resistant starch fractions, may stimulate EPS production and alter surface hydrophobicity, thereby strengthening bacterial–fiber interactions. Previous studies have reported that carbohydrate availability can modulate probiotic surface properties and enhance adhesion capacity (Ouweland & Salminen, *et al.*, 2003).

Lower adhesion values observed with pineapple fiber may be attributed to a higher proportion of insoluble fiber fractions, which may limit the availability of accessible binding sites during short incubation periods. Differences in fiber morphology, surface charge, and structural rigidity can influence the efficiency of bacterial attachment, resulting in substrate-dependent adhesion variability (Tuomola *et al.*, 2001). The progressive increase in adhesion with time further confirms that the observed reduction in optical density was not merely due to passive sedimentation, but rather reflects active and time-dependent bacterial binding to fiber particles. Adhesion kinetics suggest a dynamic process involving initial surface recognition, attachment stabilization, and potential micro-aggregate formation, as described in previous adhesion models for probiotic bacteria (Lebeer *et al.*, 2008).

Overall, these results suggest that fruit fibers, especially banana fiber, do more than just serve as food for probiotics. Along with supporting their growth, banana fiber may also help probiotics attach better and stay longer in the gastrointestinal tract. This shows that banana fiber can act both as a prebiotic and as a supportive carrier, improving the survival and effectiveness of probiotics.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The present study systematically evaluated the prebiotic potential of selected fruit fibers banana, mango, and pineapple with particular emphasis on their ability to enhance probiotic growth, stress

tolerance, and adhesion properties. The findings demonstrate that fruit-derived fibers significantly influence probiotic functionality in a strain-dependent manner, with banana fiber consistently exhibiting the strongest effects across multiple assays.

The prebiotic activity score (PAS) results confirmed that all three fruit fibers selectively stimulated probiotic growth, with banana fiber yielding the highest PAS values across the eight selected LAB isolates. This suggests superior fermentability and compatibility between banana fiber components and the metabolic machinery of the isolates. The presence of resistant starch and soluble fiber fractions in banana is known to promote probiotic proliferation and short-chain fatty acid production, thereby enhancing microbial fitness (Slavin *et al.*, 2013).

In addition to growth stimulation, fruit fibers significantly improved survival under simulated intestinal stress conditions. Exposure to pancreatin resulted in reduced survival in control conditions; however, fiber supplementation markedly increased viability percentages, particularly in the banana-treated groups. This suggests that fruit fibers not only serve as metabolic substrates but may also exert protective effects under enzymatic stress. Such protection may arise from enhanced metabolic activity, structural shielding by fiber matrices, or modulation of stress response pathways. Similar observations have been reported in studies demonstrating improved probiotic persistence in the presence of fermentable dietary fibers (Khan *et al.*, 2024).

Adhesion to dietary fibers, evaluated using the co-sedimentation assay, further reinforced the functional advantage of banana fiber. All isolates demonstrated measurable adhesion; however, adhesion percentages were highest in banana fiber treatments, particularly for Isolate 26 and Isolate 10. This enhanced adhesion may reflect favorable physicochemical interactions between bacterial surface components such as exopolysaccharides and surface proteins and fiber matrices. Carbohydrate availability has been shown to modulate probiotic surface properties, influencing hydrophobicity and aggregation behavior, which are critical for adhesion and colonization (Ouweland & Salminen, *et al.*, 2003; Lebeer *et al.*, 2008). The lower

adhesion observed with pineapple fiber may be attributed to differences in fiber composition and structural rigidity, potentially limiting accessible binding sites during short incubation periods. Variability among isolates highlights the strain-specific nature of probiotic–substrate interactions, emphasizing the importance of targeted screening in synbiotic development.

Overall, banana fiber demonstrated superior performance across growth stimulation, enzymatic tolerance, and adhesion assays, supporting its potential application in synbiotic formulations and functional food systems aimed at improving gut health. This study demonstrates that fruit-derived fibers significantly influence probiotic functionality, including growth promotion, pancreatin tolerance, and adhesion behavior. Among the tested substrates, banana fiber consistently exhibited the highest prebiotic activity score, enhanced survival under simulated intestinal conditions, and promoted superior adhesion to fiber matrices. These findings provide valuable insight into the development of functional foods and synbiotic formulations incorporating natural fruit fibers to improve probiotic efficacy. Future investigations involving epithelial cell adhesion models and *in vivo* validation studies are recommended to further substantiate these *in vitro* findings.

REFERENCES

1. Ambalam, P., Kondepudi, K. K., Nilsson, I., Wadström, T., & Ljungh, Å. Bile stimulates cell surface hydrophobicity, Congo red binding and biofilm formation of *Lactobacillus* strains. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 2012; 333(1): 10-19.
2. Ashraf, R., & Smith, S. C. Commercial lactic acid bacteria and probiotic strains-tolerance to bile, pepsin and antibiotics. *International Food Research Journal*, 2016; 23(2): 777.
3. Bosch, M., Nart, J., Audivert, S., Bonachera, M. A., Alemany, A. S., Fuentes, M. C., & Cuñé, J. Isolation and characterization of probiotic strains for improving oral health. *Archives of oral biology*, 2012; 57(5): 539-549.
4. Corcoran, B. M., Stanton, C., Fitzgerald, G. F., & Ross, R. Survival of probiotic *Lactobacilli* in acidic environments is enhanced in the presence of metabolizable sugars. *Applied and environmental microbiology*, 2005; 71(6): 3060-3067.
5. dos Santos, D. X., et al. (2019). Improved probiotic survival to *in vitro* gastrointestinal stress using prebiotic and coating approaches. *Food Research International*, 120, 62–69.
6. Holscher, H. D. (2017). Dietary fiber and prebiotics and the gastrointestinal microbiota: Mechanisms and phenotypic responses. *Annual Review of Nutrition*, 37, 389–409.
7. Jakha, K. H., et al. (2024). Mango peel powder characterization and functional potential: Prebiotic-related attributes. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 61(5), 2345–2356.
8. Khan, F., Sohail, A., Ghazanfar, S., Ahmad, A., & Riaz, A. (2024). Prebiotic Effect, Phytochemical and Functional Compounds Found in Selected Fruit Peels: A Novel Approach to Synbiotic in Phyto-Probiotics. *Applied Ecology & Environmental Research*, 22(5).
9. Khani, S., M Hosseini, H., Taheri, M., R Nourani, M., & A Imani Fooladi, A. (2012). Probiotics as an alternative strategy for prevention and treatment of human diseases: a review. *Inflammation & Allergy-Drug Targets (Formerly Current Drug Targets- Inflammation & Allergy) (Discontinued)*, 11(2), 79-89.
10. Lebeer, S., Vanderleyden, J., & De Keersmaecker, S. C. J. (2008). Genes and molecules of *Lactobacilli* supporting probiotic action. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews*, 72(4), 728–764.
11. Megur, A., et al. (2023). *In vitro* screening and characterization of lactic acid bacteria from fermented foods: Tolerance to gastrointestinal stress including pancreatin. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 134(2), 1–12.
12. Moretti, M. M. S., et al. (2025). Banana pseudostem by-product as a prebiotic source: Protection of probiotics under *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion. *Fermentation*, 11(2), 89.
13. Nath, S., et al. (2020). *In vitro* screening of probiotic properties of *Lactobacillus* spp.: Pancreatin tolerance at 0.5% as a selection criterion. *Food Quality and Safety*, 4(3), 145–152.
14. Ouwehand, A. C., & Salminen, S. (2003). *In vitro* adhesion assays for probiotics and their *in vivo*

- relevance: A review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 43(3), 289–303.
15. Raddatz, G. C., et al. (2020). Use of prebiotic sources to increase probiotic viability and survival under simulated gastrointestinal conditions. *LWT – Food Science and Technology*, 124, 109140.
 16. Ribeiro, J. A., dos Santos Pereira, E., de Oliveira Raphaelli, C., Radünz, M., Camargo, T. M., da Rocha Concenço, F. I. G., & Nora, L. (2022). Application of prebiotics in apple products and potential health benefits. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 1-14.
 17. Seneviratne, S. A. S. M., Weerasooriya, P. R., & George, D. Determination of the Acid Tolerance in *Lactobacillus* Isolated from Yogurt. *BMS The Journal of Applied Learning*, 2023; 1(1).
 18. Shehata, M. G., El Sohaimy, S. A., El-Sahn, M. A., & Youssef, M. M. Screening of isolated potential probiotic lactic acid bacteria for cholesterol lowering property and bile salt hydrolase activity. *Annals of Agricultural Sciences*, 2016; 61(1): 65-75.
 19. Shinde, T., et al. (2020). Synbiotic supplementation with prebiotic green banana resistant starch and probiotic: Functional benefit in vivo. *Nutrients*, 12(3), 1–15.
 20. Slavin, J. (2013). Fiber and prebiotics: Mechanisms and health benefits. *Nutrients*, 5(4), 1417–1435.
 21. Tatsaporn, T., & Kornkanok, K. Using potential lactic acid bacteria biofilms and their compounds to control biofilms of foodborne pathogens. *Biotechnology Reports*, 2020; 26: e00477. 25.
 22. Tokatlı, M., Gülgör, G., Bağder Elmacı, S., Arslankoz İşleyen, N., & Özçelik, F. In vitro properties of potential probiotic indigenous lactic acid bacteria originating from traditional pickles. *BioMed research international*, 2015; 1: 315819. 26.
 23. Topping, D. L., & Clifton, P. M. (2003). Resistant starch as a prebiotic and synbiotic: State of the art. *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 62(1), 171–176.
 24. Treven, P., et al. (2024). Effect of food matrix on probiotic survival during standardized in vitro digestion (INFOGEST model). *Foods*, 13(4), 678.
 25. Wang, C., Cui, Y., & Qu, X. Mechanisms and improvement of acid resistance in lactic acid bacteria. *Archives of microbiology*, 2018; 200: 195-201.
 26. Wongkaew, M., et al. (2022). Mango pectic oligosaccharides as prebiotics: Overview of probiotic utilization and benefits. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 128, 107575.
 27. Yumnam, H., et al. (2025). Assessment of potential probiotic lactic acid bacteria: Variability in 0.5% pancreatin tolerance. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 16, 123456.
 28. Zhou, Y., Cui, Y., Qu, X., et al. (2018). Prebiotic effects of dietary fiber from fruits on the adhesion of probiotics and gut microbiota modulation. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 42, 203–210.

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